

Post Quantum Cryptography Using Lattice and Cryptographic Algorithm

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By

Dr. Uma Ramachandra Pujeri

Roll No: 20SUPDROO9

Guided By

Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal

Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukks,
Mangalore, Emails: psaithal@gmail.com

**DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER ENGINEERING
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF
ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY, MUKKA,
KARNATAKA, INDIA**

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Signature :
Name : Dr. Uma Ramachandra Pujeri
Roll No : **20SUPDROO9**

Place MUKKA

Date:

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, – 574 146, Mangalore, Phone :0824-2477456

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.

Web: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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ABSTRACT

Quantum computers run faster, harder, have high computing power and hence quantum computers can solve very complex problem using fewer steps and are much faster than traditional computers. With quantum computers the attackers have high computing power and quantum algorithms there are possibilities for hackers to easily break the weak existing cryptosystem.

Traditional cryptographic algorithms are designed in such a way that breaking the cryptosystem with traditional computer's computing power will take very long time may be hundreds of years. Quantum computers on the other hand have high computer power and are faster, hence can break these existing weak cryptographic algorithms in a reasonable amount of time.

The Objective of this research is to study different traditional encryption algorithms, their weakness, study of post quantum cryptographic algorithm and design new stronger encryption algorithm.

In this research all different security algorithms were studied and implemented. Following are algorithms studied and implemented in the tenure the research

- Smart Captcha Version 1
- Symmetric Encryption algorithm
- Survey of Lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm
- Survey on RSA and Common attack on RSA asymmetric algorithm
- DNA cryptography
- Implementation of new algorithm, Hybrid Cryptosystem using two-layer DNA algorithm and RSA

Smart Captcha version 1 – Smart Captcha Version 1 which was designed and implemented is a combination of text based captcha and image based captcha where image is displayed as jigsaw puzzle. Smart Captcha Version can be easily solved by humans in few seconds but it is difficult for bots to solve the captcha in few seconds

Post Quantum Cryptography Using Lattice and Cryptographic Algorithm

Symmetric Encryption algorithm is a new encryption algorithm where plain text using secret key, ASCII value was converted from plain text to cipher text and vice versa

Survey of Lattice – In this research survey of lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm using lattice was done. In survey study of lattice, its properties and lattice based cryptographic algorithm was done

Survey on RSA and common attacks on RSA – RSA algorithm was invented by R-Rivest, A Shamir and L Adleman in 1977. RSA is asymmetric encryption algorithm used for securing data transmission over internet providing confidentiality, integrity and authentication of data and was one of the pillar to make e-commerce success over internet. In this research RSA algorithm was studied, its weakness and common attacks on RSA like low decryption exponent attack, partial key exponent attack, chosen cipher text attack, lattice attack on RSA, Shor's algorithm, Hack RSA by choosing small prime numbers were studied

DNA Cryptography - DNA encryption is the process of using computational methods to hide or scramble genetic information in order to enhance genetic privacy in the DNA sequencing process. The human genome is complex and long, but it is very possible to interpret important identifying information from smaller variations than reading the entire genome. The entire human genome is a 3.2 billion nucleotide chain of base pairs, the building blocks of life, yet genetic variation between individuals differs by only 0.5%. New strategies include various methods, such as randomized algorithms and cryptographic approaches, to anonymize an individual's genetic sequence, isolate only the essential information, and store the rest of the genome. Protects against unwanted probes. The priority now is to determine which methods are robust and how policies ensure continued protection of genetic privacy. DNA cryptography is a technique which encrypts and decrypts the plaintext using DNA sequence Adenine (A), Thymine (T), Cytosine(C), Guanine(G) In this research DNA cryptography was studied.

Implementation of New two Layer DNA-RSA hybrid cryptosystem- DNA cryptography is a current research trend on which many researcher are working. DNA cryptography is a technique which encrypts and decrypts the plaintext using DNA sequence Adenine(A), Thymine(T), Cytosine(C), Guanine(G). In our research new algorithm using two layer DNA cryptography was proposed which was added on top of RSA algorithm. Plain text mesagw was first encrypted using two layer DNA

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

RSA	-	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman.
DNA	-	Deoxyribonucleic acid
RNA	-	Ribonucleic acid
CAPTCHA	-	Completely Automated Public Turing test to tell Computers and Humans Apart
LWE	-	learning with errors
Ring LWE	-	Ring learning with errors
GGH	-	Goldreich Goldwasser Haleri
A	-	Adenine
T	-	Thymine
C	-	Cytosine
G	-	Guanine
POSET	-	partially ordered set

Chapter 1

Introduction

Quantum computers run faster, harder, have high computing power and hence quantum computers can solve very complex problem using fewer steps and are much faster than traditional computers. The attackers have high computing power with quantum computers and quantum algorithms, hence there is possibility to break the weak existing cryptosystem using quantum computers and quantum algorithms.

1.1 What is Quantum Algorithm?

Algorithm is a step by step procedure to solve the specific problem. When these step are converted to syntax of particular programming language it becomes a program and can be executed on computers to get desired output. Quantum algorithms are algorithms which can be executed on Quantum computers. In quantum algorithm instead of storing the information in bits that is either zero or ones the information is stored in qubits, the state of which is a superposition of zeros and ones. All the classical algorithms can run on a quantum computer but quantum algorithms run on quantum computers which significantly more efficient and faster than classical encryption algorithms and uses the steps in algorithm that are distinctly quantum.

1.2 What is Quantum circuits?

Quantum computations are performed using quantum circuits, where quantum gates used for steps to solve problems on one or more qubits. A quantum gate is an operation applied to a qubit that change the quantum state of the qubit. Quantum gates can be divided into single-qubit gates and two qubit gates depending on the number of qubits on which they are applied at same time.

1.3 Importance of Quantum algorithm over traditional algorithm

Traditional cryptographic algorithms are designed in such a way that breaking the cryptosystem with traditional computers power will take very long time may be hundreds of years. Quantum computers on the other hand have high computing power and are faster, hence can break these existing weak cryptographic algorithms in a reasonable amount of time. Hence quantum algorithm that are performed on quantum

computers can solve problems significantly faster than classical algorithm. The best known example are Shor's algorithm and Grover's algorithm.

Shor's algorithm is an algorithm used for integer factorization, where given a N integer the Shor's algorithm can find prime factors of integer N exponentially faster than the existing classical algorithm. Hence Shor's algorithm is quantum algorithm used for inter factorization of a integer N .

Grover's is a quantum algorithm where large, unstructured and an unordered database or a list can be search much faster than the existing classical algorithm

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1. Survey of Lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm
2. Survey on RSA and Common attack on RSA asymmetric algorithm
3. DNA cryptography
4. Implementation of new algorithm, Hybrid Cryptosystem using two-layer DNAalgorithm and RSA
5. Smart Captcha Version 1

1.4 Survey of Lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm

A set of basis vectors in a regularly spaced point grid can be referred to as a lattice. Vectors are points in a two-dimensional lattice, and a lattice is an evenly spaced vector. The origin vector are set to zero $(0,0)$. When a vector is distant from its origin vector, it is said to be long vector, and when it is close to the origin vector, it is said to be short vector.

Figure 1 – Two Dimensional Lattice

To build cryptosystems or provide security proofs, lattice-based cryptography is utilised. Post-quantum cryptography currently employs lattice-based encryption algorithms. Lattice-based cryptographic algorithms are immune to attack from both classical and quantum computers, unlike the most popular public key algorithms and key exchange algorithms like RSA, Diffie Hellman, and elliptic curve chains. With the presumption that the computational lattice problem cannot be solved effectively, lattice-based encryption algorithms are more safe. The learning with errors (LWE), Ring-LWE (ring-learning with errors) key exchange, NTRU signature, BLISS signature, and GGH (Goldreich Goldwasser Haleri) encryption scheme are some of the algorithms used in lattice-based cryptography. The traditional public key cryptographic algorithm is based on the notion that discrete logarithm factoring is difficult, as well as other related issues. However, quantum computers are able tackle factoring and discrete logarithmic problems in polynomial time. Numerous lattice-based cryptographic methods have been proven to be more secure, impenetrable by classical and quantum computers, or incapable of being solved.

1.5 Survey on RSA and Common attack on RSA asymmetric algorithm

RSA algorithm was invented by its inventors R.Rivest, A.Shamir and L.Adleman in 1977 and used for secure data transmission RSA is widely used asymmetric encryption algorithm as it's used was found securing the data transmission over internet providing confidentiality, integrity and authentication to email and was one of the pillar to make e-commerce success over the internet. RSA encryption/decryption algorithm uses receiver public key to encrypt the confidential message to cipher text and at receiver end the end user uses receiver private key to decrypt the cipher text to plain text

RSA Cryptography can be divided into two broad categories

A. Key Generation – Generating the keys for encrypting/decrypting data

Steps for key generations

- i. Choose two large prime numbers (p and q)
- ii. Calculate $n = p * q$ and $\phi(n) = (p-1) (q-1)$
- iii. Choose a number e where $1 < e <$

$\varphi(n)$

iv. Calculate $d = e^{-1} \bmod (p-1)(q-1)$

v. Private key (n,d)

vi. Public key (n,e)

B. **Encryption/Decryption Function** – Here message is converted to cipher text using public key and sender's private key while at receiver side the cipher text to plain text using public key and receiver private key.

i. Let m be message Ciphertext = $me \bmod n$

ii. Let c be ciphertext Plaintext = $cd \bmod n$

In this research RSA algorithm was studied, its weakness and common attacks on RSA like low decryption exponent attack, partial key exponent attack, chosen cipher text attack, lattice attack on RSA, Shor's algorithm, Hack RSA by choosing small prime numbers were studied

1.6 DNA cryptography

DNA encryption is the process of using computational methods to hide or scramble genetic information in order to enhance genetic privacy in the DNA sequencing process. The human genome is complex and long, but it is very possible to interpret important identifying information from smaller variations than reading the entire genome. The entire human genome is a 3.2 billion nucleotide chain of base pairs, the building blocks of life, yet genetic variation between individuals differs by only 0.5%. New strategies include various methods, such as randomized algorithms and cryptographic approaches, to anonymize an individual's genetic sequence, isolate only the essential information, and store the rest of the genome. Protects against unwanted probes. The priority now is to determine which methods are robust and how policies ensure continued protection of genetic privacy. DNA cryptography is a technique which encrypts and decrypts the plaintext using DNA sequence Adenine(A), Thymine(T), Cytosine(C), Guanine(G) In this research DNA cryptography was studied.

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1.8 Smart Captcha Version 1

Smart Captcha Version 1 which was designed and implemented is a combination of text based captcha and image based captcha where image is displayed as jigsaw puzzle. Smart Captcha Version can be easily solved by humans in few seconds but it is difficult for bots to solve the captcha in few seconds

Figure 2 – Smart Captcha Version 1

Chapter 2

Survey of Lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Lattice is any regularly spaced grid of points that extends indefinitely. Quantum safe cryptography, quantum resistant cryptography, and quantum proof cryptography are other names for post quantum cryptography. Post-quantum encryption methods are impenetrable, safe, and defense against quantum computer assault.

Lattice-based encryption is immune to attacks from quantum computers and quantum algorithms, it is a post-quantum standard that is more effective, quicker, and more secure.

2.2. Lattice Properties [2]

Important properties that lead to interesting special classes of lattices are discussed in this session.

2.2.1. Completeness

A poset is a complete lattice if all its subsets have both supremum (join) and infimum (meet). A partial ordered set ($<$, $<=$) is a complete lattice if every subset A of L has \bigwedge greatest lower bound and \bigvee least upper bound [Figure 2].

2.2.2. POSET and Lattice [3][4][5]

Let R be a relation a set A then R is a partial order on A if it is reflexive, anti-symmetric and transitive. Set A with partial ordering on R is called POSET and is denoted by (S, R)

2.2.2.1 Comparability [3]

Let x and y be elements of a POSET $(S, <=)$ then the elements x and y are said to be comparable if either $x <= y$ or $y <= x$ else x and y are incomparable. Example : - In the POSET $(Z^+, /)$ where Z^+ is set of all positive integers and $/$ is division relation then

elements 2 and 4 are comparable since $2 \mid 4$ 2 divides 4 but element 2 and 15 are not comparable since $2 \nmid 15$ since 2 does not divide 15.

2.2.2.2 Total Order

A POSET (S, \leq) is called totally ordered if every two elements of S are comparable \leq is called a total order. A totally ordered set is also called as chain.

2.2.2.3. Extremums in POSETS

Elements in POSET have external properties which are important for many application.

2.2.2.3.1 Maximal Element

An element x is said to be maximal if there is no element y which is greater than x in the POSET.

2.2.2.3.2 Minimal Element

An element x is said to be minimal if there is no element y which is smaller than x in the POSET.

2.2.2.3 Bounds in a POSET[4]

It is possible to find largest elements in a set A of POSET (S, \leq) such an element is called upper bound of A . Similarly, it is possible to find smallest element in a set A such an element is called a lower bound of A . These bounds can further be constrained as least lower bound and greatest upper bound [Figure 3].

2.2.2.4. Lattice

A POSET in which every pair of elements has both a least upper bound and a greatest lower bound is called lattice.

2.2.3 Algebra of Lattice [5]

Two binary operations Join and Meet in Lattice

2.2.3.1 Join

Least upper bound is called join of two elements and is denoted by \vee .

2.2.3.2 Meet

Greatest lower bound is called meet of two elements and is denoted by \wedge .

Identities of Join and Meet [Table 1].

2.2.4 Distributive Lattice

A distributive lattice is a lattice in which join \vee and meet \wedge distribute over each other.

For x, y, z in the lattices following is the distributive law which is satisfied

Distributive \wedge over \vee $X \wedge (Y \vee Z) = (X \wedge Y) \vee Z$.

Distributive \vee over \wedge $X \vee (Y \wedge Z) = (X \vee Y) \wedge Z$.

2.2.5 Linear Order [4]

A linear order on a set S is a (binary) relation $<$ with the following properties

- Reflexivity: $x \not< x$
- Asymmetry if $x < y$ then $y \not< x$
- Transitivity if $x < y < z$ then $x < z$
- Connectedness if $x \not< y$ and $y \not< x$ then $x = y$

Any linear order is a distributive lattice.

2.2.6 Boolean Lattice

A Boolean lattice is a POSET such that there is a element \top (a top element) such that $x \leq \top$ always holds if there is an element \perp (a bottom element) such that $\perp \leq x$ always hold

- Given element a and b there is an element $a \wedge b$ such that $x \leq a \wedge b$ holds if and only if $x \leq a$ and $x \leq b$.
- Given an element a and b there is an element $a \vee b$ such that $a \vee b \leq x$ holds if and only if $a \leq x$ and $b \leq x$

- Given an element a there is an element $\neg a$ such that $a \wedge \neg a \leq 0$ and $1 \leq a \vee \neg a$.
- Given element a, b and c we have $a \wedge (b \vee c) \leq (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c)$.

2.2.7 Complemented Lattice

A complemented lattice is bounded with least element as 0 greatest element as 1 where every element has a complement that is an element b satisfying

$$a \vee b = 1 \text{ and } a \wedge b = 0$$

2.2.8 Ortho Complementation

An Ortho complementation on a bounded lattice is a function that maps each element a to an ortho complement a^\perp such that following axioms are satisfied

$$a^\perp \vee a = 1 \text{ and } a^\perp \wedge a = 0.$$

$$\text{Involution law} - a^{\perp\perp} = a$$

$$\text{Order reversing} - \text{if } a \leq b \text{ then } b^\perp \leq a^\perp$$

2.2.9 Modular Identity

The modular identity is If $a \leq c$ $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge c$ for elements a, b, c of lattice L .

2.2.10 Birkhoff Theorem [6]

The lower set also called down set which is a subset L of X such that X is in L any $Y \leq X$ then Y is in L .

$$\text{i.e. } \forall X \in L \forall Y \in X : Y \leq X \rightarrow Y \in L \text{ [Figure 4].}$$

Birkhoff Theorem – In partial ordered set the lower sets forms a lattice in which the lattices partial ordering is given by set inclusion. The Join operation corresponds to Union. The meet operation corresponds to set intersection. Union and Intersection obeys the distributive law and this is a distributive lattice.

The Birkhoff theorem states that any finite distributive lattice can be constructed this way. All the distributive lattice can be represented by set as follows [Table 2].

2.3 Lattice Based Cryptography

Lattice-based cryptography is used to build cryptosystems or to demonstrate security. For post-quantum cryptography, lattice-based algorithms are currently in use. Quantum computers may readily defeat the most popular public key and key exchange algorithms, such as RSA, Diffie Hellman, and elliptic curve chains, but lattice-based cryptographic methods are impervious to both classical and quantum attacks. Because the computational lattice problem is thought to be intractable, lattice-based cryptography algorithms are thought to be more secure.

The learning with errors (LWE), Ring-LWE (ring-learning with errors) key exchange, NTRU signature, BLISS signature, and GGH (Goldreich Goldwasser Haleri) encryption scheme are examples of the algorithms used in lattice-based cryptography. In post-quantum public key cryptography, lattice-based algorithms are frequently utilised. The classical public key cryptographic algorithm are constructed on the fact hardness of factoring hardness of discrete logarithm and related problems. The discrete logarithmic problem and factoring, however, can both be solved by quantum computers in polynomial time. Numerous lattice-based encryption methods have been shown to be more secure, impenetrable by classical computers, and impossible to solve with quantum computers.

2.4. Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, lattice—which is defined as a collection of basis vectors in a regularly spaced grid—was explored. This survey discusses lattice properties, various lattice problems, including lattice-based cryptography. Popular encryption algorithms like the more complex AES and RSA are not immune to attacks from quantum computers. Numerous lattice-based encryption algorithms are impenetrable to classical and quantum computers or impossible to crack.

Future Work

To design post quantum cryptographic algorithm using lattice.

Chapter 3

Smart Captcha Version 1

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Captcha is completely automated public Turing test to tell computer and human apart. Captcha is software which distinguishes computer and human. Captcha provides a good security from automated bot program which are developed for automatic registration of web services to steal important confidential data. Hence in this era of internet where almost all daily activities like online shopping, online teaching, Online work, Online banking, online railway/bus/airplane ticket reservation, online bill payment etc. is done through internet, captcha provides security in the following

- Captcha can be used to make online shopping more secure
- Captcha can be used to avoid automatic registration from unwanted web services.
- Captcha is used to avoid brute force attack on online accounts for log in using different passwords
- Captcha can be used to protect the integrity of online polls by preventing the online bots to send false response repeatedly
- Captcha can protect from online bots in registration automatically to hundreds of email services which can later be used for criminal activity.
- Captcha can stop cybercriminal spamming blogs or news contents pages with dodgy comments and links to other websites

Hence captcha prevents bots to perform the malicious activities like spams in emails, misusing free web services, comments spamming in blogs, attacks in passwords systems, worms virus to hack the system through email and many fraudulent activities.

Captcha should be simple for human to solve but difficult for human to crack. Captcha should have the following characteristics

- Simple for human to solve
- Difficult for bots to solve

- Captcha should be simple, less complex and more secure
- Captcha should be easily regenerated

There are several captchas available in market with their strength and weakness. In our research we have proposed smart captcha version 1 which is updated version of smart captcha proposed in 2019. Smart captcha version 1 is a combination of text based captcha and image based captcha where image is displayed as jigsaw puzzle. Human can easily solve this captcha in seconds but it is really difficult for bots to solve this captcha

3.2 Literature Survey

Re Captcha - reCAPTCHA was created by Luis Von Ahn and was aided by a MacArthur Fellowship in 2007. reCaptcha was the most simplest captcha developed where the captcha can be solved by humans just by clicking on chek box “I am NOT Robert”. The main objective of this reCaptcha was to save time, instead of typing letters in text box for image captcha just click on checkbox “I am NOT Robot” without compromising security aspects. reCaptcha was acquired by Google in September 2009. reCaptcha uses an advanced risk analysis engine and adaptive challenge to keep malicious software from engaging in abusive activities on website

Figure 3 – ReCaptcha

Microsoft Two Layer Captcha – Microsoft developed two layer captcha in 2015. In Two layer captcha all the Characters were connected to each other from left to right.

Figure 4- Microsoft Two Layer Captcha

Gimpy Captcha – Gimpy Captcha was developed by Yahoo. Gimpy captcha selects random letters, distorts them, add noise and background and displays them

Figure 5 – Gimpy Captcha

Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle – In this captcha the entire image is broken into nine segments and all the images are dislocated. Human are still able to recognize this captcha by placing the image in correct location and identifying it but it is bit difficult for bot to recognize the image based captcha using Jigsaw puzzle.

Figure 6 - Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle

3D Captcha – In this captcha letters, digits are chosen randomly and displayed in 3D format which is difficult for bots and OCR to solve the captcha but human can solve 3D captcha very easily.

Figure 7 -3D captcha

Post Quantum Cryptography Using Lattice and Cryptographic Algorithm

Math Solution Captcha – In this type of captcha simple math equation are displayed like $3 * 5$ or $4 + 7$ or $10 - 2$ etc. These math equations are simple and human can solve but are difficult for bots to solve.

Figure 8 – Math Solution Captcha.

Sweet Captcha – In sweet captcha user should match the image rather than entering the text. In Figure 7 Drum image at right side is matched with sticks

Figure 9 – Sweet Captcha

Drag and Drop Captcha - In this type of captcha the user is asked to drag and drop specified item into circle. This captcha protects your web page from spammers and bots.

Figure 10 – Drag and Drop Captcha

Picture Identification Captcha – In this type of captcha user should identify and select the correct images from the set of images that they are asked to select

Figure 11 - Picture Identification Captcha

Tic Tac Toe Captcha – In Tic Tac Toe captcha the humans are asked to place “X” in correct position so that they get 3 X either horizontally or vertically or diagonally

Figure 12 – Tic Tac Toe Captcha

Time Based Captcha - In Time based captcha the user should solve simple math problems in few seconds. Thus time based captcha distinguishes human from bots because humans can easily solve the simple math problem and submit it while it may take time for bots to solve the captcha.

Smart Captcha - Smart Captcha – Smart Captcha is composed of text based multilayer Captcha combined with an image. The user has to recognize the text captcha and image and tick on correct check box. Smart Captcha is a time base captcha which should be solved within 10 seconds which make it more difficult for bots to solve the captcha.

3.3 Proposed System

Smart Captcha Version 1 is the extended version of smart captcha. It is implemented in Java Programming language. Smart captcha version 1 is a combination of text based

captcha and image captcha. Text based captcha is generated from digits, characters and few special symbols. The character ranges is from "A, B,C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, P, Q, S, T, U, V, W, X,Y, Z, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v,w, x, y, z" and numbers ranges from "1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9," and special characters range from "@, #, \$, &". These characters, numbers and special characters are selected randomly to generate a text-based captcha. One image is selected randomly from the database, this image is broken into pieces the pieces are dislocated and the image is displayed in scrambled format. The image and text based captcha are combined which creates smart captcha version 1. Three checkboxes are generated and one among which composes of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image. If the user ticks the right checkbox then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded. The proposed algorithm is times based, the user has to solve the captcha within 10 seconds else an error message is displayed "Time Out" and new captcha is reloaded .

A. Mathematical Model

Good Captcha - Captcha Test T which is solved by human with probability 1 as success rate whereas success rate to solve Captcha Test T for bots is negligible or nil.

Definition - Captcha Test T is said to be successful if Captcha Test T be (α, β) is human executable and at α portion of population has success greater than β over T where $(\alpha > \beta)$ and captcha Test T is NIL or negligible for bots

Proof - $C1 \in \{SC \text{ ver } 1\}$ SC ver 1 is smart captcha version 1, $C1$ is a text captcha $C2 \in \{SC \text{ ver } 1\}$ $C2$ is an image captcha

$t1$ is the time required to solve text captcha

$t2$ is time required to analyze image captcha

$t3$ is the time required to solve image captcha

$t1 + t2+t3$ is the time required to solve smart captcha by bots

t is the time required to solve the smart captcha version within 10 seconds

On input x by bot run a captcha test T for $C1$ o

If captcha test passes that is $T == x$ in time t_1 then accept x and halt. Print success captcha solved in t_1 seconds

If the captcha test does not passes that is $T \neq x$ in time t_1 second then reject and load new captcha C_1 . On input x_1 by bot run a captcha test T_1 for C_2 o

If captcha test passes that is $T_1 == x_1$ in time t_3 seconds then accept x_1 and halt. Print success captcha solved in t_3 seconds

If the captcha test does not passes that is $T_1 \neq x_1$ in time t_3 second then reject and load new captcha C_2 Let $t_4 = t_1 + t_2 + t_3$

If bot solves the captcha in t_4 seconds where $t_4 < 10$ seconds then captcha can be solved by bots else Smart captcha version 1 are unsolvable by bots in time t if and only if $t_4 > t$.

B. Algorithm

Step 1 – Initialize a character string to {‘A to Z’, ‘a to z’, ‘1 to 9’, ‘@’, ‘#’, ‘&’, ‘\$’}

Step 2 – Set maximum length of text-based captcha to 5

Step 3 – Generate each character in the text-based captcha with different colour

Step 4 – Add a background to the text-based captcha

Step 5- Randomly choose any one image from the database

Step 6 – Divide the selected image into smaller image chunks.

Step 7 – Shuffle the smaller image position and rebuild new image which is scrambled image.

Step 8 – Combine it with text-based captcha and generate a new captcha named Smart Captcha version 1 which is a combination of text and image based captcha and scrambled image captcha

Step 9 – Generate a three checkbox randomly which is composed of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image.

Step 10 - Check whether the user ticks the right checkbox. If the user ticks the right checkbox, then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded.

Step 11 – Check whether the user solves the captcha within 10 seconds.

Step 12 if the user is unable to solve the captcha within 10-second display error message "Timeout" and reload new captcha.

3.4 Results

Smart Captcha version 1 is implemented in java. Smart captcha version 1 first generates text based captcha which compromises of five characters. Following is the output of text based captcha.

Figure 13 –Text Captcha of Smart Captcha version 1

Next, the algorithm selects any one image from the database randomly. In this case, the algorithm has selected the image of a cow

Figure 14 – Image chosen randomly from database by Smart Captcha Version 1 software

This selected image is broken to smaller chunks of image

Figure 15 – Images broken into four small chunks of Image

This smaller chunk of image is shuffled and combined to form new scrambled image of cow. Following is the output

Figure 16 – Scramble Image of – Image chosen randomly from database by Smart Captcha Version 1 software Now algorithm combines this scrambled image and text-based captcha to form a Smart Captcha and following is the output

Figure 17 – Combining text captcha and scrambled image

The final output of our proposed algorithm looks like this

Figure 18 Final Output of smart Captcha version 1

When user ticks on correct option within 10 seconds the smart captcha version 1 is solved.

Conclusion

Our proposed algorithm smart captcha version 1 is clear, readable and can be solved by humans in less than ten seconds and is implemented in Java. Our captcha is composed of two parts text captcha and scrambled image captcha, the user should tick on right checkbox within 10 second which maps text for text-based captcha and text for image-based captcha. The proposed captcha was tested with 1000 users and it was more than 700 user were able to solve the captcha in less than 10seconds.

Future Work

Text-based captcha can be made more complicated by using distortion, rotation and split algorithm which is still easy for a human to recognize in few second but difficult for bots or OCR algorithms to solve in a specified time.

Chapter 4

RSA and Common Attacks on RSA

4.1 Introduction of RSA Algorithm

RSA algorithm was invented by its inventors R.Rivest, A.Shamir and L.Adleman in 1977 and used for secure data transmission RSA is widely used asymmetric encryption algorithm as it's used was found securing the data transmission over internet providing confidentiality, integrity and authentication *to email and was one of the pillar to make e-commerce success over the internet. RSA encryption/decryption algorithm uses receiver public key to encrypt the confidential message to cipher text and at receiver end the end user uses receiver private key to decrypt the cipher text to plain text* RSA Cryptography can be divided into two broad categories

1. Key Generation – Generating the keys for encrypting/decrypting data

Steps for key generations

- i. Choose two large prime numbers (p and q)
- ii. Calculate $n = p * q$ and $\phi(n) = (p-1) (q-1)$
- iii. **Choose a number e where $1 < e < \phi(n)$**
- iv. **Calculate $d = e^{-1} \text{ mod } (p-1) (q-1)$**
- v. **Private key(n,d)**
- vi. **Public key (n,e)**

2. Encryption/Decryption Function – Here message is converted to cipher text using public key and sender's private key while at receiver side the cipher text to plain text using public key and receiver private key.

- i. Let m be message
Ciphertext = $me \text{ mod } n$
- ii. Let c be ciphertext
Plaintext = $cd \text{ mod } n$

4.2 Common attacks on RSA

Attack on RSA algorithm can be classified into two categories a) Weak choice of exponent, public exponents, bad padding i.e. in setting the values of

parameters that are vulnerable to security attack b) Implementation attacks on RSA .Few RSA attacks are discussed along with their implementation in this paper

4.2.1 **Low Decryption exponent attack against RSA** – In RSA algorithm to get plain text from cipher text we use following formula $P = C^d \text{ mod } n$

Where P is the plain text, C is the cipher text, d is exponent key and n is the product of p and q. This shows that RSA decryption algorithm computational complexity is proportional to size of private exponent, which means that if the private exponent d is chosen to be very small then this may result in complete breakdown of RSA cryptosystem. In many practical applications such as smart card to improve computational efficiency the encryption process performed on low power devices tend to use small d. Choosing small d can completely break RSA cryptosystem. To understand this let us recall Chinese remainder theorem.

Chinese Remainder Theorem: If m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k are pairwise relatively prime positive integers, and if a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k are any integers, then the simultaneous congruence $x \equiv a_1 \pmod{m_1}, x \equiv a_2 \pmod{m_2}, \dots, x \equiv a_k \pmod{m_k}$ have a solution, and the solution is unique modulo m, where $m = m_1 m_2 \dots m_k$.

To demonstrate this that x can be easily computed let us take an example let Alice send message to Bob, John and Charles. Alice encrypts her message with each of the public key P1, P2 and P3, the cipher texts are $C_1 = m^3 \text{ mod } P_1, C_2 = m^3 \text{ mod } P_2, C_3 = m^3 \text{ mod } P_3$.

Now eavesdropper can easily receive C1,C2 and C3 and with these C1,C2 and C3 eavesdropper can easily recover m.

Let's assume that P1, P2 and P3 are pairwise relatively prime. By using Chinese remainder theorem, the eavesdropper computes c

$$C = m^3 \text{ mod } P_1 * P_2 * P_3$$

Since $m < P_1, P_2, P_3$ we have $m^3 < P_1, P_2, P_3$ and hence $C = m^3$. The message can now be easily computed by cube root of m.

Low exponent attack using Chinese remainder theorem, let public key P1, P2 and P3 for Bob, John and Charles be $P_1=377, P_2 = 391$ and $P_3 = 589$. Let's use $d=3$.

Alice sends Bob 330 i.e $C_1=330$ so $m^3 \text{ mod } P_1$

Therefore, $m^3 \equiv 330 \pmod{P1}$ that is

$$m^3 \equiv 330 \pmod{377}$$

Alice sends John 34 i.e $C2=34$ so $m^3 \pmod{P2}$

Therefore, $m^3 \equiv 34 \pmod{P2}$ that is

$$m^3 \equiv 34 \pmod{391}$$

Alice sends Charles 419 i.e $C3=419$ so $m^3 \pmod{P3}$

Therefore, $m^3 \equiv 419 \pmod{P3}$ that is

$$m^3 \equiv 419 \pmod{589}$$

Eavesdropper Ram uses Chinese Remainder theorem to compute message m

Eavesdropper can easily get all cipher text

$C1=330$, $C2=34$, $C3=419$ and $P1=377$, $P2=391$ and $P3=589$ where $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ are public keys of bob, john and Charles.

Therefore $0 \leq x \leq 377 * 391 * 589$

$$X \equiv C1 \equiv m^3 \pmod{P1}$$

$$X \equiv 330 \equiv m^3 \pmod{377}$$

$$X \equiv C2 \equiv m^3 \pmod{P2}$$

$$X \equiv 34 \equiv m^3 \pmod{391}$$

$$X \equiv C3 \equiv m^3 \pmod{P3}$$

$$X \equiv 419 \equiv m^3 \pmod{589}$$

Ram the eavesdropper find number $x = 1061208$

Note steps of how value of x is computed is given is table 1.1 below.

By theorem

$$X \equiv C1 \equiv m^3 \pmod{P1 * P2 * P3}$$

$$1061208 \equiv m^3 \pmod{377 * 391 * 589}$$

$$m \leq 377$$

Post Quantum Cryptography Using Lattice and Cryptographic Algorithm

$$m^3 \leq (377 * 391 * 589)$$

since $x = 1061208$

therefore $m = (1061208)^{1/3}$

$$m = 102$$

RSA Cracked message m is 102

Table which demonstrate how value of $x=1061208$ is computed using Chinese remainder theorem

Table 1 – Chinese Remainder Theorem

Sr. NO	Ci	Ni	X (Finding inverse)	Ci*Ni*Xi
1	C1= 330	N1= P2 * P3 N1= 391 * 589 N1 = 2,30,299	2,30,299 X1 \equiv 1 mod (P1) 2,30,299 X1 \equiv 1 mod (377) X1=322	= 330 * 2,30,299 * 322 =24,47,15,71,740
2	C2= 34	N2 = P1 * P3 N2 = 377 * 589 N2=2,22,053	2,22,053 X2 \equiv 1 mod (P2) 2,22,053 X2 \equiv 1 mod (391) X2=67	= 34 * 2,22,053 * 67 =50,58,36,734
3	C3=419	N3= P1 * P2 N3 = 377 * 391 N3=1,47,407	1,47,407 X3 \equiv 1 mod (P3) 1,47,407 X3 \equiv 1 mod (589) X3=574	= 419 * 1,47,407 * 574 =35,45,22,67,942
Total				60,42,96,76,416
N = 377 * 589 * 391 N = 86822723				
60,42,96,76,416 Mod 86822723 =10,61,208				10,61,208

Hence $x = 10,61,208$

Conclusion – Eavesdropper the Ram was easily able to crack RSA and retrieve message $m=102$ when $d=3$ using Chinese remainder theorem, hence security tip is to choose large value for d

4.2.2 Partial Key Exposure attack - A cryptosystem proposed by Boneh Durfee and Frankell states that modulus n is k bits long if $(k/4)$ least significant of private key d is known then the attacker can easily reconstruct the entire private key d in a linear time $(e \log(e))$ where e is the public exponent. The algorithm states that e is small the exposure of a quarter of bits of d can lead to the recovery of entire private key.

4.2.3 Chosen Cipher Attack - In Chosen Cipher text attack the attacker chooses the cipher text and recovers the plaintext original message without knowledge of private key d .

4.2.4 Shor's Algorithm – Shor's algorithm is a quantum computing algorithm for finding the prime factor's of an integer. RSA algorithm is based on the assumption that factoring large integers are intractable the statement is true for all non-quantum computing algorithms. Shor's algorithm uses quantum computers to factor the numbers in polynomial time. Shor's algorithm can be used to hack RSA algorithms and other secure data form.

4.2.5 Hack RSA by choosing small prime numbers – RSA algorithm can be defeated if the prime number p and q are chosen are small but it is difficult to defeat RSA if value of p and q are large. Sample code to hack RSA cipher with small prime numbers is provided in appendix.

4.3 Prevention and Countermeasures – Following points should be followed to make RSA algorithm stronger.

- a. Key Size – RSA key chosen should large enough to resist any security attack and break RSA cryptosystem
- b. Strong Prime – Prime Numbers p and q should be large enough. The prime factors of $(p - 1)$ and $(q - 1)$ should be large enough.
- c. Public Exponent – Public exponent e should be large enough to make RSA cryptosystem stronger
- d. Private Exponent – Private exponent should be at least 300 bits long to make RSA algorithm stronger

4.4 Conclusion

In this chapter RSA algorithm is discussed and also its weakness and common attacks on RSA like **low decryption exponent attack against RSA**, Partial Key Exposure attack, Chosen Cipher Attack, Shor's Algorithm, Hack RSA by choosing small prime numbers were discussed. In this chapter Prevention and counter measure that should be taken to avoid attacks on RSA and make RSA algorithm stronger were also discussed.

The objective of this research was to study RSA algorithm, its weakness and common attacks on RSA to write new algorithm which will make RSA stronger and prevent it from attacks.

Chapter 5

DNA Cryptography

5.1 Introduction

DNA cryptography is a technique which encrypts and decrypts the plaintext using DNA sequence Adenine(A), Thymine(T), Cytosine(C), Guanine(G)(1). One of the latest field is DNA cryptography and many researchers are working on DNA cryptography. DNA is unique for every person and is found in each cell of human body. DNA contains four bases Adenine, Guanine, Cytosine and Thymine represented as A,G,C and T. DNA sequencing refers in determining the sequence of bases in a DNA molecule. The DNA sequence of a cell encodes biological information of that cell. A single change in the position of DNA base will form totally new DNA and biological information of cell will change according to DNA sequence. In DNA cryptography message is hidden in DNA sequence. Each character in a plaintext message is converted to binary form. These binary bits are grouped into two bits and these bits are mapped to DNA base for example 00 bits are mapped to DNA base A, 01 bits are mapped to DNA base T, 10 bits are mapped to DNA base C and 11 bits are mapped to DNA base G. Now the message is converted to sequence of A, T,G,C theoretically is then physically implemented by various DNA synthesizing technique. Hybridization is a process in two complementary single stranded DNA molecules bond to form a double stranded molecule. In this process Adenine (A) always pairs with Thymine (T) and Guanine (G) always pairs with Cytosine (C). In DNA chemical synthesis method four nuclei acids A, T, C and G are added one by one to form a growing chain of nucleoids.

5.2 DNA Cryptography Encryption Algorithm

In DNA Encryption algorithm first input the message that users wants to encrypts. The string is then converted to binary. This binary string is grouped into the bits of two bits. These two bits are encoded to either A, T C or G using encoding table given in appendix. After this step fist DNA series of message is obtained. Now this DNA series message is again converted to binary string. Find one's complement. Right shift bits by three bits. This binary string is grouped into group of two bits. Encode this two binary to DNA series that is either A, T, C or G using second DNA encoding table 2. DNA

encrypted message is generated after this step. Send this encrypted message on the unreliable communication channel.

1. Step 1 – Input string from the user that has to be encrypted
2. Step 2 – Convert the inputted string to binary
3. Step 3 - Group the binary bits into group of two bits
4. Step 4 - Encode the group of two bits using encoding table1. [Note Encoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorised user. Encoding table used in mentioned in Appendix]
5. Step 5 – Create a first layer of DNA series of encrypted message using DNA encoding table 1
6. Step 6 – Layer 2: Convert the DNA series of encrypted message to binary
7. Step 7 –Find One’s complement of binary string
8. Step 8 – Left shift bits by 3
9. Step 9 – Group the bits into group of 2 bits
10. Step 10 – Encode the bits using encoding table 2 [Note Encoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorised user. Encoding table2 used in mentioned in Appendix]
11. Step -11 Create DNA series of encrypted message from encoding table 2
12. Step 12 – Send the DNA series of encrypted message to receiver

5.3 DNA Cryptography Decryption Algorithm

In Decryption algorithm the receiver receives the encrypted message. Convert these DNA series message to binary bits using decoding table. Left shift bits by three. Find One’s complement. Convert this binary string to Text string. Decode this text string using decoding table 2 to binary. Convert this decoded string to text string. Original message retrived.

1. Step 1 – Convert the DNA series message received from sender to binary using DNA decoding table [Note Decoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorised user. Decoding table used in mentioned in Appendix]
2. Step 2 – Left shift the binary bits obtained from step 1 by 3 bits
3. Step 3 - Find One’s complement of binary string
4. Step 4 – Convert the binary bits obtained from step 3 to string

5. Step 5 – Decode the string using second decoding table2. [Note Decoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorised user. Decoding table2 used in mentioned in Appendix]
6. Step 6 – Convert this decoded DNA series of binary bits obtained from step 5 to string
7. Step 7 – Original message retrieved

5.4Appendix

```
DNA_Encoding1 = {  
    "00": "A",  
    "01": "G",  
    "10": "C",  
    "11": "T"  
}
```

```
DNA_Encoding2 = {  
    "10": "A",  
    "11": "G",  
    "00": "C",  
    "01": "T"  
}
```

```
DNA_Decoding1 = {  
    "A": "10",  
    "G": "11",  
    "C": "00",  
    "T": "01"  
}
```

```
DNA_Decoding2 = {  
    "A": "00",  
    "G": "01",  
    "C": "10",  
    "T": "11"  
}
```

Chapter 6

Stronger RSA-Two Layer DNA-RSA Hybrid Cryptosystem

6.1 INTRODUCTION

Cryptography was used since ancient days where plain text was converted to cipher text using secret key and an encryption algorithm. Cryptography ensured secured communication of messages and also provided integrity, confidentiality and availability of the information Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir and Leonard Adleman(RSA) is the most widely used public key asymmetric algorithm since 1977. Researchers and cryptanalysis have looked for ways to attack RSA. In this paper we will discuss some common attacks on RSA like chosen cipher text attack against RSA like common modulus attack against RSA, Partial key exposure attack, low decryption exposure attack against RSA.

Objective – The Main objective of this research was to study RSA algorithm, its weakness and attacks on RSA and to work on to make existing RSA algorithm stronger

Proposed Work – DNA cryptography is a current research trends on which many researchers are working. DNA cryptography is hiding the data in a terms of DNA sequence Adenine (A) ,Thymine (T)

,Cytosine (C) ,Guanine (G).In our research we have proposed a new algorithm using DNA cryptography. We have added our proposed algorithm on the top of RSA algorithm to make the RSA algorithm stronger. Message is first encrypted with proposed two-layer DNA algorithm and output of this is a input to RSA algorithm.

Result and Outcome - Security analysis of proposed system has proven good. Suppose message “GOOD” it encrypted output is [114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735,

8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862] making it really difficult for hacker to guess to the message.

6.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In our proposed work we have combined two level of DNA cryptography algorithm with RSA algorithm which resulted in two level DNA RSA cryptographic system. In our proposed system the input message is first converted to series of “AGCT” text using two level of DNA cryptographic algorithm and output of this two level DNA cryptographic algorithm is input to the RSA algorithm, output of RSA algorithm is converted to asci values of string that is number making it a challenge for an intruder to break the encryption algorithm. In our proposed system values of P, Q of RSA algorithm are chosen big prime numbers, similarly e and d are of RSA algorithm chosen large numbers. Objective of this research to make RSA algorithm stronger. In this research the RSA algorithm is embedded in new two-layer DNA Computing algorithm implemented in our research center.

The Message is first encrypted using two-layer encryption algorithm and output of this encoding algorithm is input to RSA encryption algorithm. This algorithm can be used to encrypt very small secret message. The algorithm is efficient for small short message.

Input Message is Mother India

Your encrypted message is: [114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 2, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862,

25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862]

6.2.1 Modules in Encryption Algorithm

Encryption Algorithm - In encryption algorithm message is converted to binary. This binary string is encoded to DNA series message (AGCT) using secret encoding table. This is first layer of DNA cryptographic algorithm. The DNA series message is converted to binary. One's complement is done of these binary string. Bits are shifted by left by three and again these bits are encoded to DNA series message using second secret encoding table. This is Second layer of DNA cryptographic algorithm. This DNA series message encoded using second secret encoding table encryption algorithm

- Step 1 – Input string from the user that has to be encrypted
- Step 2 – Convert the inputted string to binary
- Step 3 - Group the binary bits into group of two bits
- Step 4 - Encode the group of two bits using encoding table1. [Note Encoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorized user. Encoding table used in mentioned in Appendix]
- Step 5 – Create a first layer of DNA series of encrypted message using DNA encoding table 1
- Step 6 – Layer 2: Convert the DNA series of encrypted message to binary
- Step 7 –Find One's complement of binary string
- Step 8 – Left shift bits by 3
- Step 9 – Group the bits into group of 2 bits
- Step 10 – Encode the bits using encoding table 2 [Note Encoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorized user. Encoding table2 used in mentioned in Appendix]
- Step -11 Create DNA series of encrypted message from encoding table 2

- Step 12 – Send the DNA series of encrypted message to RSA Encryption Algorithm
- Step 13 – Encrypt the output received from DNA series algorithm using RSA encryption
- Step 14 – Send the encrypted Message to the receiver

6.2.2 Module in Decryption Algorithm

Decryption Algorithm – Decryption algorithm is the reverse process of encryption algorithm. In decryption algorithm cipher text received from sender is decrypted using RSA algorithm. Output of RSA algorithm is given as an input to DNA layer 2 decoding algorithm. Message is decoded to DNA series using secret decoding table. Bits are shifted to right by 3. Find one's complement. Convert this binary to string. Decode this string using second secret decoding table. Convert the decoded binary string to string and original message is retrieved.

- Step 1 – Decrypt the message received from sender using RSA decryption algorithm.
- Step 2 – Output of RSA decryption algorithm will be input to DNA 2-layer decoding algorithm
- Step 3 -Convert the DNA series message received from DNA 2-layer decoding algorithm to binary using DNA decoding table [Note Decoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorized user. Decoding table used in mentioned in Appendix]
- Step 4 – Right shift the binary bits obtained from step 1 by 3 bits
- Step 5 - Find One's complement of binary string
- Step 6 – Convert the binary bits obtained from step 5 to string
- Step 7 – Decode the string using second decoding table2. [Note Decoding table have hidden; it is only shared with authorized user. Decoding table2 used in mentioned in Appendix]
- Step 8 – Convert this decoded DNA series of binary bits obtained from step 7 to string
- Step 9 – Original message retrieved

6.3 Experimental Analysis

This session discusses the results of the working algorithm. Session 6.1 discusses how plain text is converted to DNA two encryption algorithm and then to final cipher text using RSA algorithm. Session 6.2 discusses encryption and decryption time required for the proposed algorithm.

- 6.3.1 Encryption of Letters – A table shows the encrypted text for single letter, two letters, three letter, four letter words and five letter words.

Table 2 – Encrypted text of Proposed Algorithm

Post Quantum Cryptography Using Lattice and Cryptographic Algorithm

Sr. NO.	No Of Letters	Plain Text	DNA Two Layer Encryption Algorithm Output	Final Cipher Text
1	One let- Ter	@	GCTTGTTGGTTGGT T	[114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862]
2	Two let- Ter	My	GCTTGATTTTGT- GCTTGCTTTTGT- GATTGCTT	[114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862]
3	Three let- Ter Word	Mat	GCTTGATTTTGT- GCTTGCTTGATTG- GTTGCTTGCTTTTGT- GCTTGCTT	[114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862]
4	Four let- Ter Word	Good	GCTTGATTGCTTTTGT- GCTTGATTTTGTTTGT- GCTTGATTTTGTTTGT- GCTTGATTGCTTGGT	[114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862]
5	Five let- Ter word	World	GCTTTGTGCTTTTGT- GCTTGATTTTGTTTG T- GCTTTTGTGG TTGATTGCTTGATTT GTG	[114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862, 114735, 114735, 25862, 25862, 114735, 25862, 114735, 0, 25862, 25862, 114735, 8038, 25862, 25862]

6.3.2 Encryption and Decryption Time – Time required for encrypting the message and decrypting the message is measured in seconds. Table shows time required for one letter, two letters three letters, four letters and five letters word with respect to encryption and decryption time in seconds.

Table 3 – Encryption/Decryption Time required by proposed system

S.No	No of Letters	Plain Text	total time taken for encryption algorithm in seconds	total time taken for decryption algorithm in seconds
1	1 letter	A	0.9137299060821533	0.03386378288269043
2	2 letter	It	1.330394983291626	0.05018677711486816
3	3 letter Word	God	1.715132474899292	0.07899163246154785
4	4 letter Word	Four	1.8345668315887451	0.09565114974975586
5	5 letter Word	Fetch	2.73946475982666	0.10123300552368164

Figure 19 – Bar chart for total Time taken for encryption algorithm

Figure 19 depicts bar chart of total time taken by proposed encryption algorithm. When the plain text is single alphabet the time taken is 0.9 seconds, when the plain text is two letter the time taken to encrypts the plain text is 1.3 seconds when the plain text is three letter the total time taken to encrypt the three letter plain text is 1.7 seconds and when the plain text is four

letter word the time taken to encrypt the plain text is 1.8 seconds and when the plain text is five letter word the time taken to encrypt the plain text is 2.7 seconds. The proposed algorithm works faster to encrypt small messages like keys. Proposed algorithm is very secure for small messages.

Figure 20 – Bar chart for total Time taken for decryption algorithm

Figure 20 depicts bar chart of total time taken by proposed decryption algorithm. When the cipher text is single alphabet the time taken to decrypt is 0.03 seconds, when the cipher text is two letter the time taken to decrypts the cipher text is 0.05 seconds when the cipher text is three letter the total time taken to decrypt the three letter cipher text is 0.07 seconds and when the cipher text is four letter word the time taken to decrypt the cipher text is 0.09 seconds and when the cipher text is five letter word the time taken to decrypt the cipher text is 0.1 seconds

6.4 Conclusion

In this research we studied RSA algorithm and various attacks on RSA algorithm. To make RSA algorithm stronger the proposed work used hybrid cryptosystem combining two layer DNA algorithm with RSA algorithm. The Plain text message is given as an input to two layer DAN cryptographic algorithm output of this algorithm is an input to RSA algorithm, thus DNA layers above RSA algorithm add more security making it difficult for intruder to decrypt or break

Chapter 7

Conclusion

Encryption is a process where the plain text is scrambled to cipher text which cannot be read or understood by unauthorized user, using various encryption algorithm. Encryption plays a very vital role in protecting private, confidential and sensitive data. Thus even an unauthorized user even gets an access to sensitive data is unable to read the real hidden message in encrypted message.

In this research various traditional encryption algorithms were studied, weakness of traditional encryption algorithm over quantum cryptographic algorithm was also studied.

Research further continued with the study of RSA algorithm, its weakness and common attack on RSA algorithm. The main objective of this survey was to develop new novel algorithm which will make existing RSA algorithm stronger.

DNA cryptography which is technique which encrypts and decrypts the plaintext to cipher text using DNA sequence Adenine(A), Thymine(T), Cytosine(C) and Guanine (G) was studied. A new two layer DNA cryptographic algorithm was implemented.

In this research new algorithm “Two-layer DNA-RSA Hybrid Cryptosystem” was proposed. Plain text was first encrypted using two-layer DNA cryptographic algorithm. The output of this two-layer DNA cryptographic algorithm was given as an input to RSA algorithm and this encrypted message was again encrypted using RSA encryption algorithm where these encrypted message is stronger and harder for intruder to crack the cryptosystem.

In this research survey of lattice to design post quantum cryptographic algorithm using lattice was also done. In this survey lattice, properties of lattice, lattice problem an algorithm that provides solution to lattice problem and lattice base cryptography was studied in detail

In this research smart captcha version 1 was implemented and tested. Captcha is software which distinguishes computer and human. Captcha provides good security from automated bots program which are developed for automatic registration of web services to steal confidential data. Smart captcha version 1 is new algorithm that was implemented in Java programming language. Smart captcha version 1 is an extended version of smart captch implemented in year 2019. Smart captcha version 1 is combination of text based captcha and scrambled image.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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Publications

1. Uma Pujeri, & P.S. Aithal. (2020). Smart Captcha Version 1.
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3. Dr. Uma Pujeri#1 , Dr. P. S. Aithal*2,”Stronger RSA – Two Layer DNA-RSA Hybrid Cryptosystem” Submitted to ESCI and Scopus Indexed Journal

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PUBLISHED PAPERS

Smart Captcha Version 1

Dr. Uma Pujeri, Dr. P. S. Aithal

Dr. Uma Pujeri is a post-doctoral fellowship research scholar in Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.

Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal is Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukks, Mangalore, India.

Abstract— This is an era of internet. Life without internet is unimaginable. Even in this tough lockdown period internet plays an vital role in our life. Daily activities like online teaching, online banking, online shopping, online bill payments etc. is done through internet. However these activities can be threatened by the attacks called bots which is an automated computer program developed for automatic registration of web services to steal important credential of human data. CAPTCHA (Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell C omputers and Human Apart.) distinguishes human users and automated computer program. Captcha offers good security from automatic registration to web services. There are several CAPTCHA's with their strength and weakness. Smart CAPTCHA was proposed in 2019. Smart captcha is a Microsoft multilayer text based captcha combined with an image which can be solved using check box[site smart captcha].Smart Captcha version 1 is an updated version of smart captcha. Smart Captcha version 1 is a combination of text based captcha and image based captcha where image is displayed as jigsaw puzzle. Humans can easily solve this captcha within ten seconds but it is difficult for bots to solve this captcha.

Index **Terms**— BOTS, CAPTCHA, Image Captcha, Microsoft multi-layer Captcha, Text-based Captcha, Smart Captcha version 1, Jigsaw puzzle.

Introduction

CAPTCHA(Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell Computers and Human Apart.) is a Turing test that distinguishes human from computer. Captcha's are security check which averts hackers/spammers to get important user credentials by automatic registration to web services. Captcha prevents the bots to perform the malicious activities like spams in emails, misusing free web services, comments spamming in blogs, attacks in password system, worms, virus to hack the system through email and many fraudulent activities. Captcha should be very simple for human to solve and difficult for bots to solve. Captcha should have following characteristics [25]

1. Simple for human to solve
2. Difficult for bots to solve
3. Front end complexity should be as low as possible without compromising its security aspects.
4. Captcha should be easily generated
5. Captcha should be easily solved in few seconds or microseconds by humans. Following are few Captcha available in the market.

reCAPTCHA[7] – Most simple Captcha developed by Google search engine which simply asks user to tick on the check box ' I M NOT ROBOT'

Figure 1 reCAPTCHA

Microsoft Two layer Captcha – Microsoft deployed two layer captcha in 2015 in which all characters were connected with each other from left-to-right, top-to-bottom

Figure 2 Microsoft two layer captcha

Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle – In this captcha the pieces of images are dislocated. The user should still identify the image. Human can solve this captcha very easily where as it is difficult for bots to solve this captcha.

Figure 3 Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle

Smart Captcha – Smart Captcha is a multilayer text based captcha combined with an image which can be solved using checkbox[25].

Figure 4 – Smart Captcha

In this paper section 2 discusses survey of existing captcha, section 3 discusses the proposed system, section 4 discusses results, section 5 discusses conclusion and future work and finally the references.

REVIEW OF CAPTCHA:

A. reCAPTCHA – reCAPTCHA was created by Luis Von Ahn and was aided by a MacArthur Fellowship in 2007. The main objective to create the recaptcha was save the time require to type the letter of text based captcha with just clicking on checkbox 'I M NOT ROBOT' without compromising the security aspects. reCaptcha was acquired by Google in September 2009. reCaptcha uses an advanced risk analysis engine and adaptive challenge to keep malicious software from engaging in abusive activities on website

B. Gimpy Captcha – Gimpy Captcha is a text based captcha which selects a word or selects random letters distorts them add noise and background and display them. Gimpy captcha was build for YAHOO to keep bots away [30].

Figure 5 – Gimpy Captcha

C. Math Solution – In this type of Captcha simple math problem are displayed like $1 + 2$ or $3 - 2$ which user should solve and submit the answer in text box. The math equation are very simple, quickly solvable and easy to read[28].

Figure 6 – Math Solution Captcha

D. 3D Captcha – In this type of Captcha several 3D words is displayed which is hard for bots and OCR to recognize but can be solved by humans.

Figure 7 – 3D Captcha

E. Microsoft Two Layer Captcha – Microsoft deployed two layer captcha in 2015. In this two layer captcha the sides of each characters were connected together from top to bottom and from left to right.

F. *Picture identification of Captcha - This captcha provides the user for selecting the correct image that they have asked to identify[28].*

Figure 8 – Picture identification Captcha

G. Tic Tac Toe Captcha – This Captcha was designed for fun and involves gamification which ensures that only humans can interact with your website[29].

Figure 9 – Tic Tac Toe Captcha

H. *Sweet Captcha – This type of Captcha asks the user to match the image instead of entering text of digits in text box[29]*

Figure 10 – Sweet Captcha

I. *Drag and Drop Captcha* - In this type of captcha the user is asked to drag and drop specified item into circle. This captcha protects your web page from spammers and bots.

Figure 11 – Drag and Drop Captcha

J. *Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle* – This method the entire image is broken into nine segments and the segment are dislocated. The user should place this pieces in correct location to form the entire image and recognize it.

K. *Time Based Captcha* - In Time based captcha the user should solve simple math problems in few seconds. Thus time based captcha distinguishes human from bots because humans can easily solve the simple math problem and submit it while it may take time for bots to solve the captcha.

L. *Smart Captcha* – Smart Captcha is composed of text based multilayer Captcha combined with an image. The user has to recognize the text captcha and image and tick on correct check box. Smart Captcha is a time base captcha which should be solved within 10 seconds which make it more difficult for bots to solve the captcha.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

Smart Captcha Version 1 is the extended version of smart captcha. It is implemented in java. Smart captcha version 1 is composed of text based captcha and image. Text based in smart captcha version 1 is generated using characters, digits and few special symbols. The character ranges is from "A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, P, Q, S, T, U, V, W, X, Y, Z, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v,

w, x, y, z" and numbers ranges from "1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9," and special characters range from "@, #, \$, &". These characters, numbers and special characters are selected randomly to generate a text-based captcha. One image is selected randomly from the database, this image is broken into pieces the pieces are dislocated and the image is displayed in scrambled format. The image and text based captcha are combined which creates smart captcha version 1.

Three checkboxes are generated and one among which composes of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image. If the user ticks the right checkbox then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded. The proposed algorithm is times based, the user has to solve the captcha within 10 seconds else an error message is displayed "Time Out" and new captcha is reloaded [25].

A. *Mathematical Model*

Good Captcha - Captcha Test T which is solved by human with probability 1 as success rate whereas success rate to solve Captcha Test T for bots is negligible or nil.

Definition - Captcha Test T is said to be successful if Captcha Test T be (α, β) is human executable and at α portion of population has success greater than β over T where $(\alpha > \beta)$ and captcha Test T is NIL or negligible for bots

Proof - $C1 \in \{SC \text{ ver } 1\}$ SC ver 1 is smart captcha version 1, C1 is a text captcha
C2 is an image captcha

t1 is the time required to solve text

captcha t2 is time required to analyze

image captcha t3 is the time required to
solve image captcha

t1 + t2+t3 is the time required to solve smart captcha by bots

t is the time required to solve the smart captcha version within 10 seconds

- On input x by bot run a captcha test T for C1
 - If captcha test passes that is $T == x$ in time t1
then accept x and halt. Print success captcha solved in t1 seconds
 - If the captcha test does not passes that is $T \neq x$ in time t1 second then reject and load new captcha C1
- On input x1 by bot run a captcha test T1 for C2

- If captcha test passes that is $T1 == x1$ in time $t3$ seconds then accept $x1$ and halt. Print success captcha solved in $t3$ seconds
- If the captcha test does not passes that is $T1 \neq x1$ in time $t3$ second then reject and load new captcha

C2 Let $t4 = t1 + t2 + t3$

If bot solves the captcha in $t4$ seconds where $t4 < 10$ seconds then captcha can be solved by bots else

Smart captcha version 1 are unsolvable by bots in time t if and only if $t4 > t$.

B. Algorithm

Step 1 – Initialize a character string to {'A to Z', 'a to z', '1 to 9', '@', '#', '&', '\$'}

Step 2 – Set maximum length of text-based captcha to 5

Step 3 – Generate each character in the text-based captcha with different color

Step 4 – Add a background to the text-based captcha **Step 5**- Randomly choose any one image from the database

Step 6 – Divide the selected image into smaller image chunks.

Step 7 – Shuffle the smaller image position and rebuild new image which is scrambled image.

Step 8 – Combine it with text-based captcha and generate a new captcha named Smart Captcha version 1 which is a combination of text and image based captcha and scrambled image captcha

Step 9 – Generate a three checkbox randomly which is composed of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image.

Step 10 - Check whether the user ticks the right checkbox. If the user ticks the right checkbox then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded.

Step 11 – Check whether the user solves the captcha within 10 seconds.

Step 12 if the user is unable to solve the captcha within 10-second display error message "Timeout" and reload new captcha.

RESULTS

Smart Captcha version 1 is implemented in java. Smart captcha version 1 first generates text based captcha which compromises of five characters. Following is the output of text based captcha.

Figure 12 – Textbased Captcha of Smart Captcha ver1

Next, the algorithm selects any one image from the database randomly. In this case, the algorithm has selected

the image of a cow

Figure 13 – Image Captcha of Smart Captcha version 1 This selected image is broken to smaller chunks of image

Figure 14 – Image Chunk 1 Figure 15 – Image Chunk 2

16 – Image Chunk 3 Figure 17 – Image Chunk 4

This smaller chunk of image is shuffled and combined to form new scrambled image of cow. Following is the output

Figure 18 Scrambled Image Captcha of Smart Captcha version 1

Now algorithm combines this scrambled image and text-based captcha to form a Smart Captcha and following is the output

Figure 19 Text Captcha and Scrambled Image Captcha combined for Smart Captcha version1 The final output of our proposed algorithm looks like this

Figure 20 Final Output of smart Captcha version 1

When user ticks on correct option within 10 seconds the smart captcha version 1 is solved.

This captcha was tested with more than 1000 people and around 400 users gave a positive feedback for the proposed captcha. Many user found it easy and were able to solve it in less than ten seconds. Captcha was clear, understandable and easy to solve and hence many user rated it in between 100 to 90 points.

Feed Back Form

1. Is the captcha clear, readable and easy to solve
 Yes No Can't Say

2. Is the captcha understandable
 Yes No Can't Say

3. Does the captcha takes less time to solve
 Yes No Can't Say

4. How will you rate this captcha
 5 4 3
 2 1

5. Any other suggestion/comments

Figure 21 feedback form for smart captcha version 1

Figure 21 illustrates the feedback form for smart captcha version 1. Feedback form is composed of five points where first points ensures clarity of the captcha, because now a days there are many captcha which complicated and unreadable for the human's too. Second point checks whether the user is understanding the captcha and can solve it. Third point checks the time required for the user to solve the captcha. Now a days there are many captcha that are not solved even in 30 seconds and they simply go in infinite loop blocking our work. Fourth points in the feedback form checks the likeliness of captcha by the user. Fifth point is designed to collect some additional information.

Figure 21 Feedback of Smart Captcha version 1

Figure 21 illustrates the graph for feedback of smart captcha version 1. The graph denotes that when tested more than 400 users rated it for positively. More than 300 users were neutral and more than 200 people rated it negatively.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our proposed algorithm smart captcha version 1 is clear, readable and can be solved by humans in less than ten seconds and is implemented in Java. Our captcha is composed of two parts text captcha and scrambled image captcha, the user should tick on right checkbox within 10 second which maps text for text-based captcha and text for image-based captcha. The proposed captcha was tested with 1000 users and it was more than 700 user were able to solve the captcha in less than 10seconds.

Future Work

Text-based captcha can be made more complicated by using distortion, rotation and split algorithm which is still easy for a human to recognize in few second but difficult for bots or OCR algorithms to solve in a specified time.

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Dr Uma R Pujeri was born in Sangli, India, in 1981. She has received M.Tech degree from PSG Tech college of Engineering Coimbatore in 2008. She has received doctorate degree from Anna University Chennai in May 2017. Her research area is computer network congestion control algorithms. She has worked as an Assistant Professor in Adithya College of Engineering Coimbatore for six years. Currently she is working as an Associate Professor in MIT College Of Engineering Pune Maharashtra. She has total twelve years of teaching experience. She is a Life Member of the Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE). She has conducted several workshops, FDP and Conferences. She has total 25 publications in International journal. Her PhD thesis is uploaded on UGC

website <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/196148>.

Currently she is post-doctoral fellowship research scholar in Srinivas University, Mangalore. Her registration id is 20SUPDRO09.

Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal is a Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukks, Mangalore. He has total 29 years of teaching experience. He has completed his B.Sc. (1989) Physics, Mathematics, and Chemistry Poornaprajna College, Udupi (India). He has completed his M.Sc. (1991) Physics with Specialization in Electronics Mangalore University (India). He has completed his first Ph.D. (First) (1993-1997) Nonlinear Optical Crystals Mangalore University. He has completed his M.Sc. E-Business (2004- 2005) Manipal University. He has completed his M.Tech. in Information Technology (2009-2010) Karnataka Open University. He has completed his second Ph.D. (Second) (2005-2008) Mobile Business Manipal University. He has completed his first Post

Doctoral Fellow (2000-2001) Quantum Optics Division Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad, India. He has completed his second Post Doctoral Fellow (2002) CREOL, University of Central Florida, U.S.A. He has 48 publications in refereed International Journals/Conference Proceedings in the area of Nonlinear Optics and Photonics. He has 160 publications in refereed International Journals in Business Management and Information Technology during last 3 years. He has Presented more than 150 research papers in National & International Conferences/Seminars. He is presently guiding research scholars for their M.Phil. and Ph.D. degrees in Electronics, Information Technology and Business Management. He has Published 4 Text books with ISBN numbers and 12 Edited Conference Proceedings with ISBN numbers, 25 study books with DOI numbers. Google scholar papers = 287; Google Scholar citation = 1,171, h-index = 18; i10 index = 44; 24. Researchgate citations = 1,805; RG Score = 18.79, h-index= 23; Readers of Research Papers during last year = 37,087. SSRN last year downloads = 4,279

PAPER 2

Survey of Lattice to Design Post Quantum Cryptographic Algorithm Using Lattice.

Dr. Uma Pujeri*¹, Dr. P. S. Aithal ², Dr. Ramachandra Pujeri ³

¹ *research scholar, Computer Engineering, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India*

²*Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India*

³*Director, MIT ADT University, Loni Kalbhor, Pune, Maharashtra*

umaresearch81@gmail.com¹, psaital@gmail.com², sriramu_vp@gmail.com

Corresponding author: Phone: 8530471881*

Abstract

Objective: Quantum algorithm beat the classical computers not because they run on faster hardware but also, they require fewer steps. With Quantum computers the attackers have high computing power and with quantum algorithm can easily break the cryptographic system. Lattice can be basically thought of as any regularly spaced grid of points stretching to infinity. Quantum safe security algorithms are resistant to both attacks caused by classical computers and attack caused by quantum computers. Lattice based cryptography are the post quantum cryptographic standards which are resistant to the attacks from quantum computers hence has advantage of strong security and high efficiency. The main objective of the paper is to study lattice, lattice properties, lattice – based cryptographic algorithm to design new lattice based cryptographic algorithm which are quantum resistant in future.

Methods: In this paper the lattice-based cryptography is discussed right from its seminal work to its efficient cryptographic schemes. Paper discusses what is lattice, lattice properties, lattice problem and algorithmic solution to lattice problem and lattice-based cryptography.

Findings: After studying post quantum cryptographic algorithms using lattice it was found that lattice-based post quantum cryptographic algorithms are resistant to quantum computer attacks.

Novelty: Paper **discusses** lattice, properties of lattice in a simple way. Widely used cryptographic algorithms like RSA, Diffie-Hellman Key exchange, Elliptic Curve Cryptography are not resistant to quantum computers attacks. Paper discusses the importance of post quantum algorithm using lattice that are resistant to quantum computer attacks.

Keywords: Cryptography, Quantum Computer, Post Quantum Cryptography, Lattice, Lattice based cryptography.

1. Introduction

A lattice can be defined as a set of basis vectors in a regularly spaced grid of points. [Figure 1].

In a two-dimensional lattice vector means points and a lattices is a evenly spaced vector. For the origin vector all co-ordinates are set to zero(0,0). The vector is termed as long vector if it is far away from origin and it is termed as short vector if it is near to the origin vector. So a lattice is n linearly independent vectors where b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n are the basis of the lattices and lattices generated by this set of vectors is

$$L(b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i b_i \quad x_i \in \mathbf{Z} \text{ and } b_i \in \mathbf{R}^n \text{ [1].}$$

Quantum safe security are the algorithm which are resistant to both classical attack and several attacks done by quantum computers.

Post quantum cryptography can also be called as quantum safe cryptography quantum resistant cryptography or quantum proof cryptography. Post Quantum cryptographic algorithm are unbreakable, secure and are resistant to attack of quantum computer. Lattice based cryptography is a post quantum cryptography which is resistant, efficient and simple in implementation.

This paper discusses lattices properties, lattice problem, algorithm which provides solution to lattice problem, lattice based cryptography, conclusion and future work.

2. Lattice Properties [2]

Important properties that lead to interesting special classes of lattices are discussed in this session.

2.1. Completeness

A poset is a complete lattice if all its subsets have both supremum (join) and infimum (meet). A partial ordered set ($<$, \leq) is a complete lattice if every subset A of L has \bigwedge greatest lower bound and \bigvee least upper bound [Figure 2].

2.2. POSET and Lattice[3][4][5]

Let R be a relation a set A then R is a partial order on A if it is reflexive, anti-symmetric and transitive. Set A with partial ordering on R is called POSET and is denoted by (S, R)

2.2.1 Comparability [3]

Let x and y be elements of a POSET (S, \leq) then the elements x and y are said to be comparable if either $x \leq y$ or $y \leq x$ else x and y are incomparable. Example : - In the POSET $(\mathbb{Z}^+, /)$ where \mathbb{Z}^+ is set of all positive integers and $/$ is division relation then elements 2 and 4 are comparable since $2/4$ 2 divides 4 but element 2 and 15 are not comparable since $2 \nmid 15$ since 2 does not divides 15.

2.2.2 Total Order

A POSET (S, \leq) is called totally ordered if every two elements of S are comparable \leq is called a total order. A totally ordered set is also called as chain.

2.2.3. Extremums in POSETS

Elements in POSET have external properties which are important for many application.

2.2.3.1 Maximal Element

An element x is said to be maximal if there is no element y which is greater than x in the POSET.

2.2.3.2 Minimal Element

A element x is said to be minimal if there is no element y which is smaller than x in the POSET.

2.2.3 Bounds in a POSET[4]

It is possible to find largest elements in a set A of POSET (S, \leq) such a element is called upper bound of A . Similarly, it is possible to find smallest element in a set A such a element is called a lower bound of A . These bound can further be constrained as least lower bound and greatest upper bound [Figure 3].

2.2.4. Lattice

A POSET in which every pair element has both least upper bound and a greatest lower bound is called lattice.

2.3 Algebra of Lattice [5]

Two binary operations Join and Meet in Lattice

2.3.1 Join

Least upper bound is called join of two elements and is denoted by \vee .

2.3.2 Meet

Greatest lower bound is called meet of two elements and is denoted by \wedge .

Identities of Join and Meet [Table 1].

2.4 Distributive Lattice

A distributive lattice is a lattice in which join \vee and meet \wedge distribute over each other. For x, y, z in the lattices following is the distributive law which is satisfied

Distributive \wedge over \vee $X \wedge (Y \vee Z) = (X \wedge Y) \vee Z$.

Distributive \vee over \wedge $X \vee (Y \wedge Z) = (X \vee Y) \wedge Z$.

2.5 Linear Order [4]

A linear order on a set S is a (binary) relation $<$ with the following properties

- Reflexivity: $x \not< x$
- Asymmetry if $x < y$ then $y \not< x$
- Transitivity if $x < y < z$ then $x < z$
- Connectedness if $x \not< y$ and $y \not< x$ then $x = y$

Any linear order is a distributive lattice.

2.6 Boolean Lattice

A Boolean lattice is a POSET such that there is an element \top (a top element) such that $x \leq \top$ always holds if there is an element \perp (a bottom element) such that $\perp \leq x$ always hold

- Given element a and b there is an element $a \wedge b$ such that $x \leq a \wedge b$ holds if and only if $x \leq a$ and $x \leq b$.
- Given an element a and b there is an element $a \vee b$ such that $a \vee b \leq x$ holds if and only if $a \leq x$ and $b \leq x$
- Given an element a there is an element $\neg a$ such that $a \wedge \neg a \leq \perp$ and $\top \leq a \vee \neg a$.
- Given element a, b and c we have $a \wedge (b \vee c) \leq (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c)$.

2.7 Complemented Lattice

A complemented lattice is bounded with least element as 0 greatest element as 1 where every element has a complement that is an element b satisfying

$$a \vee b = 1 \text{ and } a \wedge b = 0$$

2.8 Ortho Complementation

An Ortho complementation on a bounded lattice is a function that maps each element a to an ortho complement $a \perp$ such that following axioms are satisfied

$$a \perp \vee a = 1 \text{ and } a \perp \wedge a = 0.$$

$$\text{Involution law} - a \perp\perp = a$$

$$\text{Order reversing} - \text{if } a \leq b \text{ then } b \perp \leq a \perp$$

2.9 Modular Identity

The modular identity is If $a \leq c$ $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge c$ for elements a, b, c of lattice L .

2.10 Birkhoff Theorem [6]

The lower set also called down set which is a subset L of X such that X is in L any $Y \leq X$ then Y is in L .

i.e. $\forall X \in L \forall Y \in X : Y \leq X \rightarrow Y \in L$ [Figure 4].

Birkhoff Theorem – In partial ordered set the lower sets forms a lattice in which the lattices partial ordering is given by set inclusion. The Join operation corresponds to Union. The meet operation corresponds to set intersection. Union and Intersection obeys the distributive law and this is a distributive law and this is a distributive lattice. The Birkhoff theorem states that any finite distributive lattice can be constructed this way. All the distributive lattice can be represented by set as follows [Table 2].

3. Lattice Problem and Algorithmic Solution to Lattice Problem

Several problems related to lattice are believed to be computationally hard in high dimension. Following are few lattice problems which are computationally hard.

- Closest Vector Problem(CVP) – Finds the closest lattice vector to a given vector[7]
- Shortest Vector Problem(SVP) – Find shortest non zero vector in lattice.
- Shortest Independent Vector Problem (SVIP) – Find n independent and short vectors.

3.1 Closest Vector Problem and Algorithmic Solution[9][10]

Closest vector problem is a computational problem on lattices which is closely related to shortest vector problem (SVP). Given a Lattice L and a target point a , CVP asks to find the lattice point which is closest to the target point a . Euclidean norms is commonly used to find the closest point to the target point. A more relaxed approach is to compute the distance of the target point from the lattice, without actually finding the closest lattice vector.

Many application of CVP only require to find the lattice vector that is not too far away from the target, it may not necessarily be closest vector. CVP is shown as NP- Hard problem in computer science. The g -approximation algorithm for CVP finds the lattice vector within the distance at most g times the distance from the optimal solution. Babai and Kannan proposed a polynomial time algorithm to solve CVP are based on lattice reduction and achieve approximation factor that are essentially exponential in dimension of lattice. The heuristic approach reasonable find good approximation to CVP is relatively less amount of time when the dimension of the lattice is sufficiently small. CVP is known as to be NP-Hard to solve approximately with any constant factor or even some slowly increasing sub polynomial function of a dimension n approximate with small polynomial factor $g = O(\sqrt{n}/\log n)$ the CVP is unlikely to be NP-Hard.

CVP is used in various cryptosystem where decryption process corresponds to CVP computation. CVP has many applications in computer science besides cryptography and finding a good CVP approximation factors that grow as a polynomial in the dimension of the lattice is one of the major open problem in this area.

3.2 Shortest Vector Problem and Algorithmic Solution[11][12][13]

The Shortest Vector problem (SVP) finds non zero vector in a lattice. Euclidean norm is commonly used to find nonzero vector in lattice for shortest vector problem. In approximation algorithm for SVP the goal is to find the non-zero lattice vector almost g (approximation factor) times the length of the optimal solution where g is usually a function of lattice dimension.

3.2.1 Exact Algorithm

There are three approaches that gives solution to the SVP in n dimensional lattice

3.2.1.1 Enumeration

They have exponential running time $n^{O(n)}$ and have advantage of being deterministic only using polynomial space. Many heuristic and optimization approach are developed which are used in practice with a moderately small dimension.

3.2.1.2 Voronoi Cell Computation

Running time of this approach to solve SVP and other lattice problem is $O(2^{2n})$ using exponential space $O(2^n)$. These are deterministic algorithm but not competitive in practice with other application.

3.2.1.3 Sieving

Running time of sieving approach is $O(2^n)$. Many heuristic approach are developed which are used in many application with small dimension ($n=40$ or $n=50$).

3.2.2 Approximation Algorithm

Approximation algorithm to shortest vector problem (SVP) by Lenstra, Lenstra and Lovaz. The LLL algorithm converts an arbitrary lattice basis into one that generate the same lattice which is reduced. Approximating SVP in the Euclidean norm is NP-Hard.

4. Lattice Based Cryptographic Algorithm[14]

Lattice based cryptography is used to construct cryptosystem or is used for security proof. Lattice based cryptographic algorithm are currently used for post quantum cryptography. Most widely used public key algorithms and key exchange algorithm like RSA, Diffie Hellman and elliptic curve can be easily attacked by quantum computers but lattice based cryptographic algorithm are resistant to the attack both classical and quantum computers. Lattice based cryptographic algorithm are more secured with the assumption that computational lattice problem cannot be solved efficiently.

Lattice based cryptography includes the algorithm such as learning with errors (LWE), Ring-LWE (ring-learning with errors) key exchange, NTRU signature, BLISS signature, GGH (Goldreich Goldwasser Halevi) encryption scheme. Lattice based cryptographic algorithms are widely used in public key post quantum cryptography. The classical public key cryptographic algorithm are constructed on the fact hardness of factoring hardness of discrete logarithm and related problems. However, both factoring and discrete logarithmic problem are solvable in polynomial time by quantum computers. Many lattices based cryptographic algorithms are found to be more secure, unhackable or unsolvable by classical and quantum computers.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper we studied lattice where lattice is defined as a set of basis vectors in a regularly spaced grid. Properties of lattice, different lattice problem, lattice based cryptography are discussed in this paper. Well

Known cryptographic algorithm like advanced AES, RSA are not resistant to attacks of quantum computers. Many lattice based cryptographic algorithm are unhackable or unsolvable by classical and quantum computer.

Future Work

To design post quantum cryptographic algorithm using lattice.

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Figures

Figure 1. Two Dimensional Lattice where points represents vector and lattice is evenly spaced vectors.

Two Dimensional Lattice

Figure 2. Complete Lattice where $a \vee b$ is the join and $a \wedge b$ meet

Complete Lattice

Figure 3. Consider set b and c then upper bound are e, g, h and least upper bound is e . The lower bound is a hence the greatest lower bound is a .

Bounds in POSET

Tables

Table 1: Identities for Join and Meet .

Sr. No	Identity	Meet	Join
1	Commutativity	$X \wedge Y = Y \wedge X$	$X \vee Y = Y \vee X$
2	Associativity	$(X \wedge Y) \wedge Z = X \wedge (Y \wedge Z)$	$(X \vee Y) \vee Z = X \vee (Y \vee Z)$
3	Idempotency	$X \wedge X = X$	$X \vee X = X$
4	Absorption law	$X \vee (X \wedge Y) = X$	$X \wedge (X \vee Y) = X$

Table 2: Distributive Lattice .

Sr. No	Distributive Lattice	Set	POSET	Boolean
1	Join Operation \vee	Union \cup	Least Upper bound (supremum)	OR
2	Meet Operation \wedge	Intersection \cap	Greatest lower bound (infimum)	AND

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SCHOOL OF COMPUTER ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY
MIT WORLD PEACE UNIVERSITY AND POST DOCTORAL
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SCHOOL OF COMPUTER ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY
MIT WORLD PEACE UNIVERSITY AND POST DOCTORAL
RESEARCH SCHOLAR IN SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE
KOTHRUD, PUNE, MAHARASH-411038
INDIAN

DR. P.S.AITHAL, DR. P.S.AITHAL
VICE CHANCELLOR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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575023-575023
INDIAN

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PUJERI
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ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR
SCHOOL OF COMPUTER ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY
MIT WORLD PEACE UNIVERSITY AND POST DOCTORAL
RESEARCH SCHOLAR IN SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE
KOTHRUD, PUNE, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA-411038
INDIAN

DR. P.S. AITHAL, DR. P.S.AITHAL VICE CHANCELLOR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALORE, KARNATAKA,
INDIA-575023
INDIAN

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Diary Number	Old Diary No	Work Title	Class of Work	Submitted By	Submitted On	Status	Documents
16618/2022-CO/L		Stronger RSA Encryption Algorithm Embedded in two-layer DNA Computing Algorithms	Literary/ Dramatic	Uma Pujeri	05/08/2022	Approval	View

Below this table, there is a section for 'List of Documents of New Application' with the following details:

Forms	Form Type	Submitted On	Status
16618/2022-CO/L	Form XIV	05/08/2022	Approval
Acknowledgment Letter	Form XIV	05/08/2022	View
Literary Work to be copyrighted	Form XIV	05/08/2022	View

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